

DEVELOPMENT AND COMMISSIONING OF AN INNOVATIVE BIOREFINERY FOR THE CONVERSION OF CONTAMINATED BIOMASS INTO HIGH-QUALITY ENERGY CARRIERS

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ABSTRACT: As a part of the EU-project “Phy2Climate” an innovative biorefinery is developed and commissioned, which uses contaminated biomass harvested from the pilot sites to produce high quality products. The center of the biorefinery is comprised of an advanced intermediate based pyrolysis process called thermo-catalytic reforming to gain intermediate products like gas, bio-oil, an aqueous phase, and biochar. These intermediates are individually refined. In case of the TCR-gas a purification step is implemented before refinement to reduce the concentration of critical gas components like NH_3 and H_2S to below 50 ppm. The aqueous phase is purified using an electrochemical process while at the same time producing hydrogen. The purified TCR-gas and the hydrogen from the electrochemical purification is used in a Gas-to-Liquid plant with the aim to produce sustainable fuels through a Fischer-Tropsch-synthesis. The so produced liquid hydrocarbons are distilled to produce gasoline (EN 228) and diesel (EN 590). The bio-oil is also refined by distillation to be used as marine fuel (ISO 8217). The produced biochar is not further refined and directly assessed as a substitute for petroleum-based coke in the copper smelting industry.

Keywords: biorefinery, thermochemical conversion, polluted soil, biofuel, innovative concepts

1 INTRODUCTION

Within the scope of the EU-project “Phy2Climate” (GA-No. 101006912) a new biorefinery is developed to transform contaminated biomass from the pilot sites into high energy carriers. The biorefinery covers in a first step the conversion of the biomass into storable intermediates of higher energy density as the original feedstock. For this, the thermo-catalytic reforming process (TCR[®]) is used [1-3]. The schematic principle of this technology is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic principle of the TCR[®] process

To prove the technical feasibility of the Phy2Climate-approach, a TCR[®] lab-scale plant is used in the project. The plant has a capacity of up to a maximum of 2 kg/h biomass to produce vapors and biochar through an advanced two-step intermediate pyrolysis-based process consisting out of an auger reactor and a subsequent post-reforming (PR) unit. The evolving vapors are being cooled down to completely condensate the liquid

fraction. This liquid is then separated into an oil and an aqueous phase for further utilization. The non-condensable gases pass through a first, coarse gas cleaning unit consisting of an electrostatic precipitator to eliminate contaminants and harmful particles inside the gas mixture [4]. The conversion process is followed by subsequently upgrading the produced intermediates to standard biofuels according to Figure 2.

Figure 2: Block scheme of the developed biorefinery

The overall biorefinery consisting out of the TCR^{®2} plant, a gas purification unit, the Gas-to-Liquid (GtL) plant, the electrooxidation unit and the distillation unit has already been commissioned. For this, a completely new gas purification unit has been built according to the purification strategy shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Gas purification strategy

In addition to commissioning of the biorefinery, first biomass conversion tests have already be done.

2 METHODS AND EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Gas purification strategy and technical design

The TCR-gas consists mainly out of the non-condensable gas components H_2 , CO , CO_2 , CH_4 and N_2 . However, it also has traces of NH_3 , H_2S and C_xH_y , which are critical for the downstream GtL in the $Phy2Climate$ biorefinery concept. The purification strategy to remove critical gas components from the TCR-gas involves an acidic and an alkaline gas scrubber for the removal of the majority of NH_3 and H_2S . It also involves a pair of fixed-bed reactors filled with Fe_2O_3 pellets to remove last traces of H_2S and a two-stage cooling trap to first remove water and after this any remains of NH_3 by liquification. Finally, it offers an additional pair of fixed-bed reactors for optional use in order to remove further critical gas components. The final result of the translation of the purification strategy into a technical design can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Technical implementation of the gas purification strategy

The commissioning of the gas purification unit was done according to a specific testing process. For this the purification unit was initially tested with nitrogen for general functionality. Within this test, the automatization of the interaction of valves and sensors had been validated. Subsequently, tests were made with a synthetic gas mixture analog to the expected composition of the synthesis gas stream from the TCR[®] process. For this NH_3 and H_2S were mixed with N_2 and inserted into the purification unit. After this the purification unit was directly connected to the TCR^{®2} plant for first real biomass conversion trials. The gas analysis of the critical gas components was done using gas test tubes (Dräger Kurzzeitröhrchen Ammoniak 2 / a).

2.2 Biomass conversion trials

Contaminated herbaceous biomass from our partners of Lithuania and Serbia was successfully converted using the TCR^{®2} lab-scale plant. For this the biomass was dried and pelletized directly in the countries of origin and afterwards shipped to Fraunhofer UMSICHT in

Germany. Figure 5 shows an overview of the so far carried-out conversion trials. The reactor temperature was kept constant at $450\text{ }^{\circ}C$ for all conversion trials, however, the postreformer temperature was varied from $550\text{ }^{\circ}C$ to $750\text{ }^{\circ}C$ for each feedstock. In total six conversion trials were done.

Feedstock origin	Used plant species for phytoremediation	Reactor temp. ($^{\circ}C$)	Postreformer temp. ($^{\circ}C$)
Lithuania	Tall fescue, Perennial ryegrass, Alfalfa, Festuca perennis, Bird's-foot trefoil	450	750
		450	650
		450	550
Serbia	Brassica napus	450	750
		450	650
		450	550

Figure 5: Overview of carried-out TCR trials

3 RESULTS

3.1 Gas purification

The designed purification unit was tested for its efficiency in removing NH_3 and H_2S using a synthetic gas mixture with nitrogen as carrier gas and NH_3 and H_2S concentrations of 3.4 % and 3.2 %, respectively. It can be seen in Figure 6, that the initial concentration of NH_3 could be reduced to less than 5 ppm. The concentration of H_2S at the outlet of the purification unit with 2 ppm was even lower. Due to this, the suitability of the purified TCR-gas as a feedstock for the Gas-to-Liquid plant has been verified and the project goal of a concentration less than 50ppm for both targeted gas components could be met.

Figure 6: Removal of NH_3 and H_2S using the designed gas purification unit

3.2 Biomass conversion trials

The mass balance of the carried-out conversion trials is shown in Figure 7. It can be seen that for both tested feedstock most of the initial mass is converted to TCR-gas independent of the used postreformer temperature. Biochar is the second largest fraction, followed by the aqueous phase and the bio-oil. The figure also visualized a clear relation of the product distribution regarding the postreformer temperature. For a temperature of $750\text{ }^{\circ}C$, 55 % of the feedstocks mass is converted into TCR-gas for the herbaceous mix from the Lithuanian pilot site and

57 % of the feedstock's mass from the Serbian pilot site. At a postreformer temperature of 550 °C the TCR-gas fraction is only about 34 % for the herbaceous mix and 32 % for the rape straw from Serbia. In contradiction to this, the fraction of bio-oil, aqueous phase and biochar are increasing for lower postreformer temperature. The losses shown in the figure correspond to product residues within the TCR-unit during the recovery of the TCR-products.

Figure 7: Mass balance of the TCR-conversion trials

Next to the mass balance, also an energy balance has been done in order to retain insights of the energy distribution within the TCR-products. For this, the results of the higher heating values (HHV) of the TCR-products given in Table and the mass fractions of the individual TCR-products were combined.

Table I: Higher heating values of the TCR-products.
*Estimated HHV for the TCR gas

Feedstock origin	PR-temp. in (°C)	Feed	HHV in MJ/kg		
			Char	Oil	Gas
Lithuania	750		13.47	34.71	15.00*
	650	16,97	15.38	29.40	14.50*
	550		14.72	34.64	14.00*
Serbia	750		14.08	34.42	15.00*
	650	13,82	15.41	34.35	14.50*
	550		16.10	32.98	14.00*

According to Figure 8 the majority of the TCR-product's energy is present within the TCR-gas. Almost 62 % of the product's energy for the herbaceous mix from the Lithuanian pilot site and 66 % for the rape straw of the Serbian site can be found in the TCR-gas for a postreformer temperature of 750 °C. In analogy to the changing mass distribution for lower PR-temperatures, the energy distribution within the TCR-products also shifts in favour of biochar and bio-oil. The energy content of the aqueous phase is not considered in the energy balance as it normally has a specific energy content less than 0.2 MJ/kg [1].

Figure 8: Energy distribution of the TCR-products.
Assumption HHV of gas at PR-temp.: 750°C/15MJ/kg; 650°C/14.5 MJ/kg; 550°C/14MJ/kg

4 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

From a technical point of view the first period of the Phy2Climate project was mainly focused on commissioning a fully operating lab-scale biorefinery for a maximum feedstock capacity of 2 kg/h of dried contaminated feedstock. This has been achieved by combining already existing plant parts with newly designed ones like the gas purification unit. By means of the gas purification unit NH₃ and H₂S concentrations in the TCR-gas far below the targeted project concentration of 50 ppm can be realized. Due to this, the TCR-gas can be directly used within the downstream GtL process. Next to successfully commissioning the biorefinery first conversion trials have been done, showing the interplay of the individual biorefinery parts. Also, first mass and energy balances of the carried-out conversion trials have been prepared. According to those balances the provided feedstock convert mainly to gas, followed by biochar, the aqueous phase and bio-oil.

The second half of the project will focus on the refinement of the TCR-products and its applicability as biofuels according to international standards. The results will be announced in future scientific publications.

5 REFERENCES

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